

Changing Acceleration Rate (Cosmological Constant) Endogenous to Empirical Fractal Cosmology Model

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Abstract

This paper supplements the author's fractal-cosmology paper by discussing recent DESI Survey observations that suggest the cosmological constant (λ) may not be constant throughout the universe's evolution and may be weaker than it was earlier in the universe's evolution. While these findings are at most a 4.2 sigma, this observation is extraordinary and demands an explanation.

In the author's 2024 paper, [Experiment on Inverted Fractal Corresponds with Cosmological Observations and Conjectures](#), the changing acceleration rate of expansion with respect to time and distance was empirically found to be a property of a growing fractal, along with Hubble-Lemaitre and accelerated expansion. In this paper, this finding was re-presented in the context of the DESI observations. The fractal, the geometry of our time, explains and predicts, independently, these phenomena and thus should be part of the discussion.

Keywords: Cosmological Principle, Dark Energy, Hubble-Lemaitre's Law, Quantum Gravity, Quantum Cosmology, Λ CDM

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent observations from the DESI Survey[1] have revealed that the so-termed 'Dark Energy'— linked to the cosmological constant (λ)—central to the standard 'lambda, cold dark matter' (Λ CDM) model of the universe, may not be constant throughout the evolution of the universe; that it is weaker than it was earlier in the universe's evolution. While these findings are at most a 4.2 sigma [2], they are extraordinary and demanding explanations.

A model known to cosmology, though rejected as an explanation for the evolution of the universe, may explain or even predict this paradox and other paradoxes associated with the standard model of cosmology; it is the fractal?

In 2022 and 2023 researcher Blair D. Macdonald published two papers respectively in the International Journal of Quantum Foundations; Speculations, the first on the quantum and the fractal: [The Fractal Corresponds to Light and Quantum Foundation Problems](#) [3]; and the second on the large-scale structure of the Cosmos and the fractal: [Experiment on Inverted Fractal Corresponds with Cosmological Observations and Conjectures](#) [4]. In the latter paper, Macdonald modelled a growing fractal and empirically measured and analysed its growth, concluding that cosmological observations correspond almost precisely with fractal evolution. His model addressed the claims of the 2012 WiggleZ Dark Energy Survey [5], which refuted the fractal cosmology hypothesis, and showed that the observed initial and increasing hierarchical clustering, scaling to a 'smooth' origin, is consistent with what one would expect in a

growing fractal structure. The model explicitly demonstrated Hubble expansion and accelerated expansion and was supported by the demographics and distribution of galaxies. One property of the inverted fractal model predicted was that the acceleration rate of the growth of the fractal increases with time and should be able to be observed. This prediction is now consistent with recent DESI observations.

In this paper, the author highlights the fractal's property and its derivation. Is this unexpected changing acceleration rate of the fractal and of the universe—to everyone involved, including the author, if observations further suffice—a coincidence, or evidence that the universe behaves as a growing fractal? If so, do the standard fractal cosmology hypothesis and its refutation need to be reviewed?

2 Position within an Emergent Fractal

Macdonald places the observer in an isolated fractal and accounts for what would be observed looking forward (his first 'quantum-fractal' paper) and what would be observed looking backwards or behind (his second paper). He used the Koch snowflake fractal (Figure1, below) for simplicity, where 'a' is 'looking forward, and 'b' is 'looking behind'.

The schematics above demonstrate fractal development by (a) the (classical) forward or evolving Snowflake perspective, where the standard-sized thatched (iteration '0') is the focus, and the following triangles diminish in size from colour red iteration 0 to colour green iteration 2. (b) The inverted retrospective perspective assumes a fixed location within the fractal. The new (thatched) triangle is the focus and is held at a standard size, while the original red triangle (iteration 0) expands in area as the fractal iterates.

Figure 1. Dual Perspectives of (Koch Snowflake) Fractal Growth.

In his first paper, the author, from this position, viewed forward, and concluded this perspective is was parallel, as paradoxical and complex, as foundational quantum problems. In his second paper, Macdonald applied kinematic methods, measuring changes relative to previous points as the fractal grew.

From Figure 2 below, the author measured distances(d) and inferred displacement (D) from a fixed location in a growing Koch snowflake fractal.

Measuring the blue line displacement (D) and the red line distance (d) from an observer (t_4) to the triangle centre points inside an iterating Koch Snowflake fractal. t = iteration-time.

Figure 2. Measurement of Displacement and Distance Inside a Fractal.

While Macdonald used the Koch Snowflake to conduct his measurements, he used a growing tree, a common fractal, as the best analogy to describe his findings. “It is as if the observer is on a branch of a (fractal) tree surrounded by branches of similar age and size and is looking back—down—to the trunk of the tree, which was the origin of the tree and has now expanded.”

Macdonald was clear that the universe is only similar to a tree structure in that it grows like a fractal, and that the trunk (‘of the tree’), of which the farthest galaxies surround us and possibly the CMB origin, as demonstrated in Figure 3 below. In his paper, Macdonald justified the tree analogy by finding that trees increase volume with age and that the large quasar structures observed in the outer universe correspond to the bough (first branches from the trunk) location on the fractal tree.

Complementary to Macdonald’s work, all trees in nature have been found to accelerate with age[5],[6].

(a) The DESI Map of the Universe[7] with observation rings from clustered 'small scale' (light blue) to the smooth (large structured LQGs) outer universe (blue and light-yellow rings). (b) Observing from high in the branches of an oak tree (fractal), looking down and back to the trunk with corresponding universe observation rings; (c) observing from the trunk of an oak tree (fractal), looking up and out to the branches.

Figure 3. Non-isotropic and non-homogeneous universe observations corresponding with a living tree fractal

3 Fractal Expansion and Acceleration Rates

The following diagrams and equations are empirically derived from a spreadsheet model of an inverted fractal developed by Macdonald. The first, Figure 4 (Figure 10 in the original paper), pertains to the Hubble-Lemaître Diagram [8]. The second, Figure 5 (Figure 11 in the original paper), concerns acceleration and changes in acceleration between receding points on the growing fractal as a function of time or iteration.

3.1 Fractal Expansion

As the (exponential) distance between triangle geometric centres increases with iteration-time, the recession velocity of the points increases. cm = centimetres.t= iteration-time.

Figure 4. The Fractal Hubble-Lemaitre diagram.

3.1.1 Fractal Hubble Equation

Equation 1, (equation 21 in the original paper) pertains to Figure 4, The Fractal Hubble-Lemaitre diagram and is the Fractal Hubble equation and Fractal Hubble Constant. The Fractal Hubble line is described by:

$$v = F_v D \quad (1)$$

“where (F_v) is the slope of the line of best fit, where the fractal (Hubble) recession velocity is constant.” It explains Hubble’s Law. Macdonald added: “The scale invariance of the Fractal-Hubble diagram concurs with the historical development of the Hubble diagram through the ages. From its 1929 original to the improved 1931 to its most recent, the shape of the diagram remains constant, just as with the fractal model.”

3.2 Fractal Acceleration

As the distance between triangle geometric centres increases with iteration, the recession acceleration of the points increases. cm = centimetres, t = iteration-time.

Figure 5. Recessional Acceleration vs. Distance on the Inverted Koch Snowflake Fractal.

3.2.1 Fractal Macdonald Equation

The following equation, derived from his model, predicts an increasing rate of cosmic acceleration. It can be inferred (from this inverted fractal model) that the accelerating expansion of the universe concerning distance (Figure 5) is a growth property of fractal geometry, and described by the equation

$$a = F_a d \tag{2}$$

where F_a is the fractal (cosmological) recession acceleration constant measured in units of $cm^{-1}t^{-2} cm^{-1}$. The constant F_a in equation 1 (18 in the original paper) may be interpreted as a fractal, a ‘cosmological constant’—lambda—concerning point acceleration and distance. “

The constant F_a in equation 2 that Macdonald deduced **is not** the cosmological constant—lambda—concerning point acceleration and distance, but is the constant of increasing acceleration rate with respect to distance and time. From the perspective of the observer, the acceleration rate is lowest there, and is greatest at the—past—origin.

4 Conclusions in Discussions

While the study concerns cosmology, the changing acceleration rate with growth is a property of fractals. It is a law of all fractals.

Notwithstanding this serendipitous finding from Macdonald that may explain the increasing cosmological constant, it is now a property that cosmologists and astronomers should monitor, given that many other properties are endogenous to the fractal model and are evident in cosmological observations.

Notably, the inverted fractal model predicts three expansion-related properties that have now been observed.

1. Points recede away from the observer and in accordance with the Hubble-Lemaitre expansion.
2. These points accelerate away from the observer in accordance with dark energy and cosmological constant conjectures;
3. From the observer position, the acceleration rate of the receding points decreases with time. It is greater in the past.

The following is from the original fractal cosmology paper:

“The fractal model offers a direct geometric solution to the quantum gravity problem, that the quantum and the observed cosmos are different sides of one emergent fractal geometry. Looking ‘back’ into the fractal corresponds with cosmological observations; looking ‘forward’ into the fractal from an in-situ observation point corresponds with ‘the quantum’[3]. Together—and with further exploration—fractal geometry will complete the knowledge gap. The fractal may open the door to a quantum unification and so-called quantum gravity. This simple geometric model does not take away from General Relativity; it complements it. Gravity is independent of the fractal model.

According to cosmological observations, the universe behaves exactly like a growing fractal. If we had no cosmological observations but only the mathematics of fractal geometry to inform predictions about the structure and evolution of our universe, and if, based on the ubiquity of fractals in our Earthly reality, we expected to observe the universe we currently observe, then we would expect to observe the universe we currently observe. This is not the first time geometry has resolved observational discrepancies or paradoxes; one need only look to how circles, and later ellipses, explained and ended a paradigm. Fractals are the geometry of our time.”

The fractal cosmology hypothesis requires review, and the (apparent) fractal law of decreasing acceleration rate with time of growing fractals warrants discussion.

5 References

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